

Exploring Security Issues in Abia State.

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Abstract

*This study aims at assessing community policing and security in Abia State. Survey method was adopted and simple random sampling was used to select respondents, while the data analysis was done using the chi square technique. The results of the study were presented using tables, frequencies and percentages. The results indicate that the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) have performed poorly in controlling crime in various localities. Also, majority of the respondents (30.8 percent) agreed that Nigeria Police Force are unfriendly to the general public. It was also observed that the confidence level of the citizens towards the NPF is very low as 53.3 percent of the respondents agreed to not having confidence in the NPF in the area of crime control. Based on public opinion, the relationship between members of the public and the NPF in general is very poor. This study discovered that community policing, through the **Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC)**, has succeeded in assisting the Nigeria Police in internal security and welfare provision. It is recommended that there is need to enhance the existing communication system between the police and the communities, particularly through the use of mobile phones and other means of communication whereby members of the public can easily reach-out to the police as the need arises.*

Keywords: Exploring, Security, Issues, Abia State.

Introduction

Crime and insecurity cases seem to be on the increase in Nigeria in recent times notwithstanding the concerted efforts of various security agencies, especially the police in ensuring peace and security of life and property. The rising trend of insecurity is largely reflected in the increasing incidents of armed robbery, kidnapping, human

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trafficking, assassination, terrorism, militancy, etc., in various parts of the country (Osakwe, 2009). Insecurity, without a doubt, is one of the major problems confronting Nigeria, especially in the last ten years. This situation is very worrisome considering the basic responsibility of government and state to lives and property of Nigerians as reflected in the 1999 constitution (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2011). In 2019, Nigeria was listed among the 15 most vulnerable nations in the world (Obidiegwu and Elekwa, 2019). This position did not only corroborate the internal security situation, but also confirmed the increasing loss of capacity by respective governments to perform basic security and developmental functions despite repeated claims of huge budgetary allocation and expenditure on security of lives and property (Njoku, 2012; Newswatch, 2010).

Nigeria is presently battling with a growing security problem, which is progressively threatening its sovereignty and development. The domestic security challenges in Nigeria is so alarming such that there is ethnic conflict in the North, kidnapping in virtually all parts of the country, militancy and oil pipeline vandalism in the Niger Delta Region; terrorism and religious extremism by Boko Haram in the North East, self-determination agitations by the Independent People of Biafra (IPOB) and the Movement for the Actualisation of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB); cattle rustling and herdsmen disturbances in the North and Central Regions, ritual killings in the South and West Region, with Abia State noted for fatal kidnappings and armed robbery (Ukoji and Okolie- Oseneme, 2016; Onime, 2018).

Attempts have been made by various administrations in Abia State towards addressing the security situation. Former Governor T.A. Orji invited the Nigerian military to Aba to quell the insecurity in Aba in particular and Abia in general. The incumbent Governor (as at the period of writing this research), Governor Okezie Ikpeazu has donated vehicles to the Abia State Police Command so as to boost the war against criminals in the state (Nwagboso, 2012; Okoro, 2015).

The problems of engaging in corruption, bribery, incivility, injustice, torturing, maltreating, extra-judicial killings, and accidental discharge by members of the police force which results in killing innocent people within the nation is alarming. These factors have battered as well as dented the image of the Nigeria police force which is the major problems of concern. In fact, another factor militating against the members of the

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Nigeria police force while executing their lawful duties is obstructions by some habitual criminals who may not want the police to checkmate and curb crimes and criminal activities going on within their various environments in Abia State. The issue of reforming, transforming and rebranding our environments to be peaceful and secure place of inhabitation of the entire populace of Abia State is a welcome development. The people living in the country side, that is, the rural dwellers have not been able to receive good impacts and correlate very well with the security incentives and other related services offered by the Nigeria police force. It is through the process of community policing that strong partnerships will be generated between the members of various communities and the Nigeria police force. Interestingly, this will bring about protection of life and property at the grassroots level in our various rural communities. The members of the Nigeria police force can as well obtain relevant information that will enable them prevent and curb crimes and criminal activities through positive interactions with the members of the various communities. The major problem here is that some community leaders like the village heads, and their executive members may collude with these habitual criminals living among them as well as harbouring them because of the ill gotten money they make as returns with them. This has deterred the Nigeria police in maintaining total security law enforcement and peaceful coexistence in the location under study.

Study Area

The study area, Abia State, is located in the south eastern part of Nigeria between latitudes $4^{\circ}45'E$ and $6^{\circ}00'N$ of the Equator, and Longitudes $7^{\circ}00'E$ and $8^{\circ}09' N$ of the Greenwich Meridian. It is bordered by Imo State in the East and politically shares common boundaries with Anambra, Enugu and Ebonyi State to the North West, North and North East, respectively. To the East and South East, it is bounded by Cross River and Akwa Ibom States and by Rivers State to the South. It comprises four (4) regions (Aba, Bende, Isuikwuato and Afikpo) and was created from Imo State in 1991. It has 17 Local Government Areas (L.G.As) including Aba North, Aba South, Arochukwu, Bende, Ikwano, Isiala Ngwa North, Isiala Ngwa South, Isuikwuato, Obi Ngwa, Ohafia, Osioma Ngwa, Ugwunagbo, Ukwa East, Ukwa West, Umuahia North, Umuahia

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South, Umu Nneochi, respectively. The capital city is Umuahia, and major commercial city is Aba. It is one of the nine constituent states of the Niger Delta Region.

Figure 1: Abia State

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Literature Review

Security is seen as the degree of resistance to, or protection from harm. It applies to any vulnerable and valuable asset such as a person, dwelling, community, nation, or organization. According to Agozino (2020), security could be referred to as a measure that ensures peaceful co-existence and development at large. It is implied from Agozino's view that with the existence of security, there is absence of fear, threat, anxiety, tension, and apprehension over the loss of life, liberty, property, goals and values, among others. As Adekola and Enyiche (2017) rightly pointed out, security could mean different things at different times to different people. It is perhaps imperative in this paper to come to certain terms with what sort of security is deliberated here. This is because by the term *security*, one could mean food security, financial security, personal security, energy security, environmental security, cyber security, national security, among others.

The term *security* according to Akinyemi (2021), is the situation that exists as a result of establishment of measures for the protection of persons, information and property against hostile persons' influences and nations. It is the existence of condition within which people of the society can go about their normal activities without any threat to their lives and properties. Security, however, can be described as stability and continuity of livelihood, predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect), protection from crime (feeling safe), and freedom from psychological harm, safety or protection from emotional stress which results from the assurance of knowing that one is wanted, loved, accepted and protected in one's community or neighbourhood and by people around (Achumba et al., 2013).

Security is a concept that is prior to the state and the state exists to promote that concept (Agozino, Emmanuel, Augustine and Patrick, 2021). Security is the prime responsibility of the state. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria specifically states that "the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary concern of the government". It is not an exaggeration to state that the constitutional responsibility of Nigerian government to provide security for her subjects has in one way or the other failed due to the inability of government to provide a secure and safe environment for lives and properties and even that of economic activities.

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Security is about the management of threat and it is often thought of as the pursuit of freedom from threat. Security requires specification of both a threat, and a target object. Threats are about the possibility of harm coming to a valued referent object. The concept of security within the national space has been defined within the context of national security; a term that defines the dynamics and interrelationships between internal security which refers to threats from within the country and external security which touches on trans-national threats.

The term *security* as used here, can be understood as national security. As national security, Campbell (2020) viewed it as referring to “a state where the unity, well-being, values, and beliefs, democratic process, mechanism of governance and welfare of the nation and her people are perpetually improved and secured through military, political and economic resources. Cavalcanti (2020) traditionally understood national security as the acquisition, deployment and use of military force to achieve national goals.

For Gordi (2021), the concept of National Security cuts across many disciplines, covering military protection, surveillance, protection and human rights. Providing an implicit sense, Torti (2016), saw national security as the ability of a nation to preserve its internal values from external threats. Hence, “national security implies the appropriation and deployment of state apparatus of coercive force to deal with situation of crisis, nationally or internationally”.

Within this perspective, Jore (2017) defines national security as "the absence of threats to acquired values and subjectively, the absence of fear that such values will be attacked. Professor Charles Maier of Harvard University similarly defines the concept through the lens of national power by noting that national security is best described as a capacity to control those domestic and foreign conditions that the public opinion of a given community believes necessary to enjoy its own self-determination or autonomy, prosperity and wellbeing (Maier, 1990). Also highlighting the intertwining relationship between internal and external security within the context of national security, Moshe Keinan defines national security as;

The dynamics of a state's ability and readiness to deal effectively with external threats caused by rival states and rival organizations, and deal effectively with internal

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threats caused by parties inside the society, which put in risk the physical existence of the state's population, its identity, its values and its vital interests (p.25).

Aside these, some authorities have attempted to define national security in terms of demographic threats occasioned by epidemics, natural disasters, climate change and other events causing severe environmental damage and the ability of the state to emplace an effective emergency response plan to swiftly protect it from or rehabilitate the populace in the event of such occurrence.

The argument here is that National Security is infused with two important dimensions. These are Internal Threats and External Threats. Internal security, which is concerned with internal threats is all state actions directed at emplacing, upholding and deploying national laws, strategies, policies and state law enforcement agencies towards the maintenance of peace, law and order; safeguarding citizens from fear or threats to their values, livelihood, liberty, lives and property within a country's territory. While there are usually several secondary law enforcement agencies that are statutorily empowered to advance the internal security interests of a nation, the Police is commonly acknowledged as the lead agency within the internal security framework of any nation.

In contrast, external threats within the context of national security is, according to Harold Brown, U.S. Secretary of Defense (1977-1981), the primary responsibility for guaranteeing external security by the Military of a nation and where this is undertaken in conjunction with other security agencies, the military will, under an ideal situation, take command and control pre-eminence in such operational relationships.

To other scholars, security is the absence of threat to acquire values or tendencies that would undermine national cohesion and peace as criteria for the determination of the meaning of security. Security is the condition or feeling of safety from harm or danger, the defence, protection and absence of threat to acquire values (Olawole, 2018).

Insecurity on the other hand is the antithesis of security. It is the extreme opposite of security. The import of this is that it is pertinent to conceptualize security before insecurity. Security is seen as political, economic, social and environmental threat that affects the individual as well as the state at national and international levels. Belend (2015) defined insecurity as "the state of fear and anxiety stemming from a concrete or alleged lack of protection"; it refers to lack or inadequate freedom from danger. Insecurity is also seemed as the state of being subject to all forms of dangers of both

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natural and artificial disasters with mostly resulting from human activities towards society or individuals. In the same way, Udoh (2015) sees insecurity as the state of being subject to danger or injury. The anxiety that is experience when one feels vulnerable, insecure and lack confidence.

However, because of the very many ways in which insecurity affects human life and existence, the concept of insecurity has usually been ascribed different interpretations in association with the various ways which it affects individuals. Some of the common descriptors of insecurity include want of safety; danger; hazard; uncertainty; want of confidence; doubtful; inadequately guarded or protected; lacking stability; troubled; lack of protection; and unsafe, to mention a few. All of these have been used by different people to define the concept of insecurity. These different descriptors, however, run into a common reference to a state of vulnerability to harm and loss of life, property or livelihood.

Insecurity as an antithesis of security refers to a condition that exists due to lack of effective measures put in place to protect individuals, information and property against hostile persons, influences and actions. Insecurity is simply a situation in which individuals in a given society cannot go about their daily activities as a result of threat to and harmful disruption of their lives and property. According to Belend (2015), insecurity entails lack of protection from crime (being unsafe) and lack of freedom from psychological harm (unprotected from emotional stress resulting from paucity of assurance that an individual is accepted, has opportunity and choices to fulfill his or her own potentials including freedom from fear.

Research Design

The research design that was used for the study is the survey method. Survey methods are excellent vehicles for measuring attitudes and orientations in a large population. Also, as a descriptive research, the researcher would simply describe the issue under investigation. The essence of descriptive design is to specify the properties of the problem under investigation.

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Table 3.1 Research Data Sets

S/N	VARIABLES	UNIT OF MEASUREMENT
1	The state of security	Types/Number
2	The activities of community policing	Methods/Number
3	The Impact of community policing	Type/Number
4	The implementation of community policing	Type/Number
5	Factors militating against community policing	Type/Number
6	The strategies for improving community policing	Strategy/Number

Population of the Study

The study was undertaken in the three Senatorial Districts of the State where fifty (50) Community Policing Officers each were selected from the 17 Local Government Areas. To this end, the target population constitutes of 850 Community Policing Officers (respondents) from all the existing local government areas in Abia State.

Determination of Sample Size

In 2020, projected population for Abia State was 31,243,203. Interestingly, the population of the study comprise community policing officers to be recruited in the State. The population of study is 850. To determine the sample size of the study, the researcher used Cochran's (1977) formula for calculating sample size when population size is finite. Cochran pointed out that if the population is finite, then the sample size can be reduced slightly. This is due to the fact that a very large population provides proportionally more information than that of a smaller population.

Cochran proposed correction formula to calculate the sample size:

$$n = \frac{no}{1 + \frac{(no-1)}{N}}$$

Here, n is the sample size derived from equation and N is the population size,

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while no is Cochran's constant

$$n = \frac{752}{1 + \frac{(752-1)}{850}}$$

$$n = \frac{752}{1 + 0.88}$$

$$n = 400$$

To this end, the sample size of the study is four hundred (400) respondents.

Sampling Techniques

The study adopts simple random sampling technique. Simple random is a sampling technique where every member of the population has equal and independent chance of being selected in the sample to be studied. The equality of chance for each number of the population is the most distinguishing feature of simple random sampling. This technique is used in order to give equal chance of representation to all the respondents of the target population and also aids in minimizing the degree of bias that could have injected into the selection of the respondents.

Data Collection Technique

The questionnaire and personal interviews were used to gather the primary data while intensive review of literature in libraries, reports, journals, magazines, and other materials of interest served as sources of secondary data.

Results

This section deals with the socio-demographic profile of the surveyed respondents such as gender, educational qualification, occupational distribution and marital status.

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Table 4.1 : Gender Distributions of Respondents

Gender	No. of respondents	Percentage
Male	306	76.5%
Female	94	23.5%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

As contained in Table 4.1 above, 306 respondents representing 76.5% were males while 94 respondents representing 23.5% were females. The research was more particular about gender status and the sensitive nature of the topic under study.

Table 4.2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	No. of respondents	Percentage
18-30 years	86	21.5%
31-40 years	197	49.3%
41-50 years	69	17.3%
51 -Above	48	12 %
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The age distribution Table (Table 4.2) shows that 21.5% (86) of the respondents are between 18 - 30 years, while 49.3% (197 respondents), 17.3 % (69 respondents) and 12% (48 respondents) fall between 31 – 40years, 41 – 50 years and 51 and above, respectively. The implication of this distribution is that majority of the respondents are still within the working and productive age.

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Table 4.3: Marital Distributions of Respondents

Marital status	No. of respondents	Percentage
Single	130	32.5%
Married	210	52.5%
Divorced	40	10%
Others	20	5%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The marital status distribution on Table 4.3 shows that 130 respondents representing 32.5% were single, 210 respondents representing 52.5% were married, while 40 (10%) and 20 (5%) respondents were divorced and others marital status, respectively. The analysis shows that most of the respondents are married and were not faced with emotional problems that may affect the reliability of the study.

Table 4.4: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Qualifications	No. of respondents	Percentage
FSLC	80	20%
SSCE	167	41.8%
OND/ND	50	12.5%
HND/B.SC	62	15.5%
OTHERS	41	10.3%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

On the educational qualification of the respondents, the surveyed data indicate that majority of the respondents, at least, had basic education. Of the 400 valid respondents, 80 or 20% had FSLC, 167 or 41.8% had SSCE, 50 or 12.5% had ND/NCE; 62 or 15.5% had HND/B.Sc., respectively, while 41 (10.3%) had other degrees. The essence of securing information on the respondents' qualification was to be sure that they relatively understood what the study was all about and thereby, to some extent, were able to contribute to the study under investigation.

Table 4.5: What are your Feelings about the Relationship between the Police and Members of the public?

Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Very Poor	103	25.8%
Poor	127	31.8%
Very good	91	22.8%
Excellent	79	19.8%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

It can be observed from Table 4.5 above that 103 respondents which represent 25.8% have a very poor relationship level with the NPF; 127 respondents which represent 31.8% have a poor relationship level with the NPF; 91 respondents which represent 22.8% have a very good feeling of relationship with the NPF; 79 respondents which represent 19.8% have an excellent relationship with the NPF. Based on public opinion, the relationship between members of the public and the NPF in general is very poor as citizens do not have a strong bound with officers of the NPF.

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Question: What are the challenges facing the smooth operation of policing in Nigeria?

Do you think that the underfunding of the Nigerian Police Force has affected its Performance?

Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Strongly agreed	120	30%
Agreed	160	40%
Disagreed	56	14%
Strongly disagreed	64	16%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

From the table above, 120 respondents which represent 30% strongly agreed that the NPF is underfunded; 160 respondents which represent 40% agreed to this, 56 respondents which represent 14% were of the opinion that the NPF is not underfunded, and 64 respondents which represent 16 strongly disagree with the above statement. From this , it can be seen that majority of respondents are of the opinion that the underfunding of the NPF has affected its performance in carrying out its constitutional duties.

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Does the creation of other policing agencies have negative impacts on the Performance of the Nigeria Police Force?

Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Strongly agreed	56	14%
Agreed	64	16%
Disagreed	132	33%
Strongly disagreed	148	37%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The above table depicts that 56 respondents which represent 14% strongly disagreed; 64 respondents which represent 16% agreed; 132 respondents which represent 33% disagreed, while 148 respondents which represent 37% strongly disagreed with the claim above. Majority of the respondents claimed to strongly disagree that the creation of other policing agencies does not affect the performance of the NPF

Grossly inadequate logistics and equipment (especially transportation, arms and ammunition, etc.) affect police performance?

Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage
Strongly agreed	120	30%
Agreed	160	40%
Disagreed	56	14%
Strongly disagreed	64	16%
Total	400	100%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

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From the table above, 120 respondents which represent 30% strongly agreed, 160 respondents which represent 40% agreed; 64 respondents which represent 16% disagreed, and 56 respondents which represent 14% strongly disagreed. Majority of the respondents agreed that inadequate logistics and equipment affect the performance of the NPF.

Collaborations between the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) and Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC) in Abia State

In our unstructured interview on 28th August 2021 with the Police Public Relations Officer (PPRO), Zone 9, Umuahia, she revealed that, through providing financial and material support, the Abia State Government is making tremendous efforts towards addressing the security situation. However, the increasing security threats in Abia State (rising cases of kidnapping, human trafficking, armed robbery, rising unemployment, among others) reinforces the analytical importance of attempting an evaluation of community policing expressed through the PCRC aid to the Nigeria Police, Abia State Command in ensuring the maintenance of domestic security and bridge the gap between the police and the public. Therefore, Table 14 below represents the Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC) achievements in Abia State.

Some Selected Contributions of Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC) to Policing and the Nigeria Police Force, Abia State Command

S/N	Material and Financial Contributions
1	Printing of fliers on security tips for the public and organising sensitization and orientation programme for Abia State Secondary School students on grass-root security
2	Passed useful information to the Nigeria Police that have led to the recovery of stolen cars and other crimes in Abia State.

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3	Sinking of borehole and assisting in the renovation of the Police Officers' Mess, Umuahia and the expansion of the Division Police Officers' office at Umuokpara, Umuahia North Local Government Area
4	Financial and material contributions to Police Children School in Umuahia and Aba areas
5	Free medical treatment for 250 policemen and women in Abia State Police Command
6	Chairman PCRC, Amb. Emma Nwosu personal donation of 10 sewing machines to Nigeria Police Officers' widows through CP Adamu; donation of 50 bags of cement to the Nigeria Police Force, Abia State Police Command for renovation activities; donation of delivery kits to MOPOL 55 Clinics and helping in the building of the police armoury. Payment of N96,000 for medical operation of Cpl. Gabriel of MOPOL 55; providing two times free medical treatment for all officers, wives and children of MOPOL 55 Squadron. Donation 750 wrappers to all women in MOPOL 55 during the time of CSP. Dankwano. Donation of N200,000 for the Police Church Chapel building project and settling of N600,000 worth of medical bills at Living World Hospital, Aba for men and women of the Nigeria Police Force, among other contributions.
7	Central Police Station (CPS) Aba, Abayi, Osisioma, Akwette, Uratta, Bende, World Bank, Umuobiakwa and Arochukwu Police Divisions - building of conference hall, security tower, toilet facilities, perimeter fence, borehole and provision of electricity generating sets
8	Construction of a two-bedroom bungalow for the Divisional Police Officer and security tower at Ndegoro Police Division
9	Donation of brand new vehicle to Osisioma Police Division by one of the patron

Sources: Data provided by the Police Public Relations Officer (PPRO), Abia State Police Command in face-to-face interview, 28th -31st August, 2018 and additional information supplied by the State Chairman, Police Community Relations Committee, Abia State on 31st August, 2021.

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Examining closely Table 14 above, it could be seen that in Abia State, the PCRC has significantly fostered community policing and enhanced internal security between 2014 and 2017. This study observes that the PCRC forum in Abia state has created and enhanced good relationships between community members; the community and the police, hence, fostering group participation in proffering solution to security problems confronting the communities. Generally, it could be seen from the Table 1 above that the PCRC generally stands in the gap between the police and the public and as such, community policing practitioners in Abia state renders sizeable and commendable level of financial and material assistance to the Abia State Police Command. Thus, the potency and effectiveness of community policing through the PCRC forum in Abia state shows that their involvement in policing activities has helped to reduce the level of crime and stress on the Nigeria Police Force.

Deductions from the Table 14 above and information gathered revealed that the relationship between the Nigeria Police, Abia State Command and the public is largely cordial. Also, this study discovered that PCRC is functioning effectively at some Divisions, while it is not working effectively at some divisions. Again, in our interaction with some Senior Police Officers (names withheld), they revealed to us that one, the rate at which members of the public volunteer useful information is not encouraging. Two, the lack of essential equipments for the Police is hindering the effectiveness of community policing. Three, the discouraging lack of confidence and trust by the public on their own police is a source of concern.

Discussion of Findings

The information gathered revealed that the relationship between the Nigeria Police, Abia State Command and the public is largely cordial. Also, this study discovered that PCRC is functioning effectively at some Divisions, while it is not working effectively at some divisions. Again, in our interaction with some Senior Police Officers (names withheld), they revealed to us that one, the rate at which members of the public volunteer useful information is not encouraging. Two, the lack of essential equipments for the Police is hindering the effectiveness of community policing. Three, the discouraging lack of confidence and trust by the public on their own police is a source of concern.

The findings of the study also revealed that the community police collaborate

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with the police to a high extent in Abia State. This shows that the said group work together with the police in community policing functions to ensure protection of lives and properties of community members. Thus, both the vigilante and police collaborate effectively in crime control. This may be because there exists a cordial relationship between the vigilante and the police in Abia State. This relationship if maintained will yield fruitful security results in the State. This finding is in agreement with Adejoh (2013), who affirmed that policing function is more effective when it is carried out as a collaborative and collective responsibility between the vigilante and the police.

In addition, Phenson (2014) noted that every successful security operation is dependent upon effective planning and extent of intelligent information sharing between the vigilante and the police. However, Okunola (2011) observed that there was poor rate of crime reporting to the police and vigilante by community members and this affected the effectiveness of the police and vigilante in minimizing crime. This may be one of the reasons why sales and consumption of hard drugs is still high in some communities in Abia State. In addition, the study reveals that the vigilante provides police with report on how to trace and control the menace of cattle herdsmen to a low extent. The poor rate of crime reporting by some community members to the vigilante may affect timely sharing of intelligent information between the vigilante and the police.

In this instance, Umar and Bappi (2014) affirmed that information sharing between the vigilante, community members and police will help to develop cooperative and collaborative ties for the purpose of crime prevention, crime reduction and maintenance of law and order. The test of the null hypothesis showed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of policemen serving in the urban and rural areas on the extent to which vigilante collaborated with the police in minimizing crime in Abia State. Thus, policemen serving in the rural and urban areas agreed that the vigilante collaborate with the police in the war against crime in Abia State. It is worthy of note at this point that community policing should not be seen as a sole preserve of the vigilante and the police, but an integrated effort by all and sundry to wage war against crime and enthrone law and order in every community.

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Conclusion / Recommendations

The results of this study indicates that the Nigeria Police Force (NPF) has performed poorly in controlling crime in various localities. Majority of the respondents (30.8 percent) agreed that Nigeria Police Force are unfriendly to the general public. It was also observed that the confidence level of the citizens towards the NPF is very low as 53.3 percent of the respondents agreed to not having confidence in the NPF in the area of crime control. Based on public opinion, the relationship between members of the public and the NPF in general is very poor. The study also discovered that community policing, through the **Police Community Relations Committee (PCRC)**, has succeeded in assisting the Nigeria Police in internal security and welfare provision.

Therefore, the study suggests that Nigeria populace should build more trust and confidence in the police, and that the Nigerian populace should change their mindset towards the police as their own. The Nigeria Police on the other hand, need to be more professional in their dealings with the public. They should respect the fundamental human rights of the public, be civil and friendly to the people whom they serve. This will build more police-community confidence, thereby enhancing domestic security.

To ensure that national security and peace is maintained in Nigeria, crime prevention must be seen as everybody's business and not the responsibility of a few police or men in the community. Findings have revealed that women play a vital role in crime prevention being that they are victims of crimes; they can offer first-hand information when tracking down offenders. The role women play both as victims and managers of crimes therefore, calls for an all-inclusive gendered programming in the prevention and management of crimes. This will enhance the participation of women and empower them in both communication and sensitization approaches to crimes.

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